

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA.

D2.2 Safety monitoring system development

Project acronym: ACCESSAFRICA 2

Grant Agreement no.: 101103296

Lead contractor for this deliverable: Uganda National Drug Authority

Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101103296
Project Acronym:	ACCESSAFRICA 2
Project Title:	Strengthening Clinical Trial Regulatory and Ethical Review Oversight in East Africa
Title of Deliverable:	D2.2 Safety monitoring system development
Work Package:	WP2
Due date according to contract:	30/06/2024
Contributor(s):	Marvin Buleera
Reviewer(s):	Diana Kesi Nakitto, Andrew Rutebuka
Report Approved by	Dr. Helen Byomire Ndagije, Prof. Rosemarie Bernabe

Consortium Partners:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	University of Oslo	UiO	Norway
2.	Partner	Uganda National Health Research Organisation	UNHRO	Uganda
3.	Partner	Jimma University	JU	Ethiopia
4.	Partner	Uganda National Council for Science and Technology	UNCST	Uganda
5.	Partner	National Drug Authority	NDA	Uganda

BACKGROUND

One of the objectives for Work Package 2, 'To develop a safety monitoring system to monitor trends in safety reporting that can be accessed by all regulators.' To achieve this objective User Requirement Specifications have been developed. These contain details of the Clinical Trials Serious Adverse Events (SAE) reporting functionality.

These have been attached for your reference

NATIONAL DRUG AUTHORITY

Safe Drugs Save Lives

Integrated Regulatory Information Management System

Clinical Trials Module

Serious Adverse Events Reporting

Sub Module

User Requirements Specifications

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Document Approval

	Name	Title	Date	Signature
Author	Marvin Buleera	Inspector of Drugs	18.04.2024	
Reviewed by	Diana Kesi Nakitto	Manager Clinical Trials	18 April 2024	
Checked by	Andrew Rutebuka	Ag. Head Information Communication Technology	18 th April 2024	
Approved by	Dr Helen Byomire Ndagije	Director Product Safety	18 th April 2024	

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Table of Contents

Document Approval	2
Introduction of the module	3
Business Case.....	4
Purpose of the module.....	5
Applicants.....	5
The Authority.....	5
Ethics and Regulatory Reviewers [NRIMS].....	5
Goals and Objectives.....	6
Business Process Analysis	6
i. New SAE Report Submission.....	6
ii. Follow-up SAE Report.....	7
iii. Final SAE Report Submission.....	7
Process Map	8
New SAE Report Process Map.....	8
Follow-up SAE Report Process Map.....	9
Final SAE Report Process Map.....	10
Process Definitions	11
Process User Classes.....	11
Use Cases.....	11
Definitions.....	13
Annexes	14
Annex I Serious Adverse Events Form.....	14

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Introduction of the module

This User Requirement Specification details Clinical Trials Serious Adverse Events (SAE) Reporting functionality in NDA.

The system will have the following functionalities;

1. New SAE Report
 - a. Provision for submission of a new SAE report against an approved Clinical Trial.
 - b. Provision for attachment of additional information
 - c. Provision for requests for additional information
2. Follow-up SAE Report
 - a. Provision for submission of follow-up reports
 - b. Provision for requests for additional information
3. Final SAE Report
 - a. Provision for submission of a final report.
 - b. Provision for requests for additional information

Business Case

1. Manage SAE Reports at each review cycle
2. Manage the submitted SAE Reports from applicants.
3. Receive SAE Reports submitted
4. Distribute SAE Reports for review
5. Conduct reviews
6. Generate indicators and chart analysis (Review status, Research type)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

- i. Clinical Trial SAE Database
 - ii. Register of clinical trials and historical information on clinical trials
 - iii. Summary information on SAE Report processing
 - iv. Service Delivery Timeline Analysis
 - v. Conformance to the Customer Service Charter
7. Notification for timely submissions of reports
8. Provision of feedback to stakeholders on collated data

Purpose of the module

The module will enable

Applicants

- Submit SAE Reports to the Regulatory Authority (NDA) and supporting documents online
- Track the progress of the review of SAE Reports from the authority
- Provision for submission of additional information
- Receive computerised regulatory acknowledgements on submissions as per the stipulated timeline
 - Acknowledgements
 - Any other feedback

The Authority

- Receive notifications when SAE Reports are submitted
- Assess and review the submission from the beginning to the end of the review cycle electronically (cycle management)
 - Schedule and allocate reviewers to review SAE Reports electronically

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

- Reviewers assess and review the SAE Reports electronically.
- Monitor the progress of the SAE Reports; review online and alert reviewers of delays
- Generate acknowledgements and any other feedback.
- Ad hoc reporting tools – allow for generating custom reports.

Ethics and Regulatory Reviewers [NRIMS]

- Integration to NRIMS from the portal.
- Access to the status and information of the submissions for SAEs.
- Validation of the SAEs from the ethics committee.

Goals and Objectives

- i. To develop a high-quality [efficient, reliable, and user-friendly] system that allows for electronic submission, assessment/review, and feedback to the applicants for clinical trials.
- ii. To develop a system that facilitates communication between the two main users (Authority, and Researchers)
- iii. To develop a system that exports data from the online submission and review process to Excel and/or PDF format for printing and saving backups
- iv. To develop a system with dashboards for monitoring and evaluation.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Business Process Analysis

List of processes and processes maps. The module provides management of the following processes:

- i. **New SAE Report Submission**
 - a. The applicant accesses the system using the given link with the approved credentials.
 - b. The applicant selects the Clinical Trial to be reported on.
 - c. The applicant completes and submits the SAE Report.
 - d. Receipt and acknowledgement of SAE Report.
 - e. The manager assigns a reviewer.
 - f. The SAE review is carried out.
 - g. A reviewer can ask for additional information on the SAE Report.

- ii. **Follow-up SAE Report**
 - a. The applicant accesses the system using the given link with the approved credentials.
 - b. The applicant selects the Clinical Trial to be reported on.
 - c. The applicant proceeds to choose the initial SAE Report they are following up on.
 - d. The applicant completes and submits the SAE Report.
 - e. Receipt and acknowledgement of SAE Report.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

- f. The manager assigns a reviewer.
 - g. The SAE review is carried out.
 - h. A reviewer can ask for additional information on the SAE Report.
- iii. **Final SAE Report Submission**
- a. The applicant accesses the system using the given link with the approved credentials.
 - b. The applicant selects the Clinical Trial to be reported on.
 - c. The applicant proceeds to choose the initial SAE Report they are following up on.
 - d. The applicant completes and submits the SAE Report.
 - e. Receipt and acknowledgement of SAE Report.
 - f. The manager assigns a reviewer.
 - g. The SAE review is carried out.
 - h. A reviewer can ask for additional information on the SAE Report.
 - i. The SAE is then closed off.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Process Map

New SAE Report Process Map

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Follow-up SAE Report Process Map

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Final SAE Report Process Map

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Process Definitions

Process User Classes

Id	Name	Description	Role Name	Role Dependency
1	Submitting of Clinical Trial SAE Reports	Submits Clinical Trial SAE Reports	Clinical Trials SAE Report submission	Applicant
2	Receiving of Clinical Trial SAE Reports	Receives Clinical Trial SAE Reports	Clinical Trials SAE Report receipt	CT Unit
3	Review of SAE Reports	Review of the Clinical trial SAE Report submitted	Review of Clinical Trials SAE Reports	CT Unit
4	Communication	Sending out information to applicants	Communication	CT Unit

Use Cases

Use Case: Receiving of Clinical Trial SAE Report form			
Use Case ID	CT001	Primary Business Actor	CT Manager
Use Case Name	Receiving of Clinical trial SAE Reports	Other Participating Actors	CT Officer, Applicants
Module/Sub-module	Clinical Trials SAE Reports	Triggers	Conducting a clinical trial /study in Uganda
Special Requirements	Approved Clinical trial application	Pre-condition	Approved Clinical Trial
Goal	Check if all fields and documents required are submitted.	Post Condition	
Purpose	Review of the Clinical Trial SAE Report		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Business Rules	1. The submitted clinical trial SAE Report should be attached to an approved Clinical Trial.		
Detailed Specification	Receives clinical trial SAE Report electronically		
Data		Data Verification	
Data Location	Hard copies and soft copies with CT		
Reports	Review report.		

Use Case: Review of Clinical Trial SAE Report			
Use Case ID	CT002	Primary Business Actor	CT Officer
Use Case Name	Review of Clinical Trial SAE Reports	Other Participating Actors	CT Manager
Module/Sub-module	Clinical Trials SAE Reports	Triggers	Submission of an SAE Report
Special Requirements	Approved Clinical trial application	Pre-condition	
Goal	Check if all fields and documents required are submitted.	Post Condition	
Purpose	Review of the Clinical Trial SAE Report		
Business Rules			
Detailed Specification	Review a clinical trial SAE Report through CT		
Data		Data Verification	
Data Location	Hard copies and soft copies with CT		
Reports	Review report.		

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

Use Case: Communication with applicants			
Use Case ID	CT003	Primary Business Actor	CT Officer
Use Case Name	Communication with applicants	Other Participating Actors	CT Manager
Module/Sub-module	Clinical Trials SAE Reports	Triggers	Allocation of an SAE Report
Special Requirements	Approved Clinical trial application	Pre-condition	
Goal	Provide feedback to the applicant	Post Condition	
Purpose	The applicant knows what the Review outcome is		
Business Rules			
Detailed Specification			
Data		Data Verification	
Data Location	Hard copies and soft copies with CT		
Reports	Acknowledgement letter		

Definitions

- **Use Case Name:** The name that represents the goal that the use case is trying to accomplish.
- **Use case ID:** Identifier that uniquely identifies the use case.
- **Purpose:** Short description outlining the purpose of the use case and its activities.
- **Primary Business Actor:** A stakeholder that primarily participates and benefits from the use case by receiving something of measurable or observable value.
- **Other Participating Actors:** Other actors that participate in the use case to accomplish its goal including initiating actors, facilitating actors, sever/receiver actors and secondary actors.
- **Precondition:** A constraint on the state of the system before the use case can be executed. Typically, this refers to another use case that must be previously executed.
- **Postcondition:** Change in the state of the system once the use case executes successfully, e.g., data recorded in a database or a receipt is delivered to a customer.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCPT3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

- **Business Rules:** Refers to conditions governing the behaviour of a particular Use Case. These may include policy-specific criteria, e.g., Prices are the same throughout the country.
- **Data:** Important data associated with a particular use case.
- **Data Location:** Current location of data associated with a particular use case.
- **Data Verification:** System or manual verification of data associated with a particular Use Case.
- **Purpose:** The summarized reasons for the use case.
- **Reports:** The information, including queries, that can be generated from the system by users.
- **Triggers:** Events that occur for a use case to begin.
- **Goal:** Successful user outcome
- **Detailed specification:** Process that's required to reach the outcome

Annexes

Annex I Serious Adverse Events Form

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.

This project is supported by the Global Health EDCTP3 Joint Undertaking and its members.

NDA Clinical Trials Serious Adverse Event (SAE) FORM

NDA CTA Number Study Acronym

Study Title

Study Site

Report type: Initial Report: Follow-up report

Participant ID	Study arm	Age (years)	Gender	Weight	Height

SAE (MeDRA term)

SAE onset date Stop date..... Ongoing:
 (DD/MM/YYYY) (DD/MM/YYYY)

Date of site awareness

NARRATIVE OF THE SAE

(Describe the SAE including details of physical examination, actions taken and admissions, etc)

Laboratory tests	Results (comment on normalcy)

Investigations (Imaging, ECG, etc)	Results (comment on normalcy)

SUSPECTED DRUGS (Include generic name)

Drug name	Formulation	Dosage	Route of administration	Indication
.....
Start date	End date	Ongoing <input type="checkbox"/>		
.....			
Manufacturer name and address				

CONCOMITANT DRUGS (Include generic name)

Drug name	Formulation	Dosage	Route of administration	Indication
Start date	End date	Ongoing <input type="checkbox"/>		
Manufacturer name and address				

OTHER RELEVANT HISTORY

e.g. diagnostics, allergies, pregnancy with last month of period, etc.

Seriousness Criteria: Life threatening Disabling/incapacitating
 Prolonged hospitalization Death Congenital anomaly
 Other Medically important condition

Is this reaction expected? Expected Unexpected

CAUSALITY ASSESSMENT

Tool: WHO-UMC tool NARANJO OTHER (Specify)

Causality:

Definite Probable Possible Unlikely Unrelated

Conclusion on relatedness

To the IMP: to Medical Device: to disease condition: Non-IMP drugs

Severity of the event

Mild Moderate Severe Life threatening

Outcome of the event

1	Recovered	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	If Yes Date
2	Improved/Improving	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	If Yes Date

3	Ongoing	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	If Yes Date
4	Worsened	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	If Yes Date
5	Fatal	Yes <input type="checkbox"/>	No <input type="checkbox"/>	If Yes Date

Was the drug stopped? YES NO

Other cause of event (Specify)

Has the adverse event been reported to the Sponsor? YES NO

Date of Report:(DD/MM/YYYY)

Reviewed by:

Principal Investigator: Signature Date.....